

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Report on DSL development in NEMO and IFS-FVM
Deliverable D2.3**

EuroHPC
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1. Abstract /publishable summary

Heterogeneous supercomputer architectures have advanced significantly in recent years, incorporating multi-node parallelism and graphics processing units (GPUs) to create larger and more energy-efficient systems. At the same time, climate models are growing increasingly complex, computationally demanding, and time-intensive. GPUs are becoming crucial for speeding up scientific applications, and by leveraging their processing power, climate researchers can accelerate simulations and more quickly explore a wide range of climate scenarios.

This work shows the enhancements made so far on DSL development in NEMO and IFS-FVM models with the aim of allowing the targeting of these models on GPUs. In particular, the document summarizes the progress made when PSyclone DSL in NEMO and GT4Py DSL in IFS-FVM are used.

2. Conclusion & Results

The experiments conducted so far show that using PSyclone to generate a GPU-ready version of the code is a complex task, particularly for non-standard configurations, and requires significant fine-tuning. Currently, several modules of NEMO are not yet supported by the PSyclone *acc_kernel* transformation causing, probably, the lack of performance using GPUs. Moving forward, the goal is to manually optimize the generated code for better performance and to collaborate with the PSyclone developers to extend the OpenACC transformation scripts or create new ones to enlarge the PSyclone processing step to those NEMO files that were excluded until now. Moreover further investigations are also needed to find the optimal tuning for the GPU utilization to maximize performance in order to maximize the exploiting of the device capabilities.

The IFS-FVM nonhydrostatic finite-volume dynamical core has been implemented entirely in Python with the GT4Py domain-specific framework. The global configuration is based on the latest version of GT4Py which is actively developed and refined alongside the numerical model implementation. The presented tests show that the ported model can already effectively use the latest CPU and GPU hardware. The latest version of GT4Py will be further optimised and the distributed multi-GPU extension of the model (not yet available for this report) will be tested and compared systematically to the current operational IFS in 2025. Results from multi-GPU scaling and portability studies across different GPU based architectures with the more advanced regional configuration of the model are presented, which indicate the significant potential of the GT4Py approach for large allocations across computing systems with GPU accelerators.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology for efficient and scalable simulations of weather and climate across the Earth system modelling community in Europe.	Yes
A2: Close common technology gaps in the knowledge and toolbox for high-resolution Earth system modelling via joint developments across the European community.	Yes
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub for training, communication, and dissemination for high-performance computing for weather and climate modelling in Europe.	No

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Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	Yes
O2: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	Yes
O3: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modelling.	No
O4: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	No
O5: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	No
O6: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth system science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	No

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Deliverable D2.3 describes the outcomes achieved in WP2 task 2 concerning the exploitation of two Domain Specific Languages, PSyclone and GT4Py, for porting respectively NEMO and IFS-FVM to GPU-based architectures.

PSyclone is a source-to-source code generation and transformation tool designed to enhance performance portability and maintainability for weather and climate codes written in Fortran. NEMO, a widely used ocean model in the climate research community, is used to build two key CMCC configurations: the regional model MED24 and the global high-resolution model GLOB16, both of which are described in the following sections. The computational performance of these configurations have been evaluated on the hybrid nodes of the CMCC supercomputer. Part of this work has been documented in the Milestone M2.3. New insights have been reported in the section “4.3. Experimental configurations” and “4.4 Tests and Performance Analysis”.

GridTools for Python (GT4Py) is a Python library designed to produce high-performance implementations of stencil kernels commonly used in weather and climate modeling. By systematically separating domain-specific code from performance engineering, GT4Py provides a distinct advantage. This approach facilitates ongoing adaptation to emerging hardware technologies and enables targeted optimizations for specific hardware platforms. PMAP (Portable Model for Multi-Scale Atmospheric Prediction) is the python version, developed with GT4Py, of the non-hydrostatic finite-volume dynamical core developed for the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) at ECMWF. Two configurations of PMAP have been evaluated in this task.

4.1. Models description

In the following section the NEMO ocean model and the IFS-FVM are described.

4.1.1 NEMO

NEMO is a widely used ocean modelling platform that supports a large user community engaged in research and forecasting services in oceanography and related sciences. Developed and maintained by a European consortium, including institutions like CNRS and Mercator-Ocean (France), NOC and the Met Office (UK), and CMCC (Italy), NEMO allows the creation of various configurations based on the NEMO-OCE ocean model, which simulates ocean dynamics and thermodynamics using primitive equations. Additionally, NEMO can be extended with two modules: NEMO-ICE, which models the dynamics, rheology, and thermodynamics of sea ice, and NEMO-TOP-PISCES, which focuses on ocean tracer transport and biogeochemical processes.

NEMO is distributed with several “Reference Configurations” that provide the most important features and capabilities, making it easier for users to set up their first application while also helping developers to test and check the new developments. For the global configurations the ORCA tripolar grid is used in the model (Figure 1), in order to cover the entire oceanic domain without singularity points.

Unlike the regular grids formed by meridians and parallels, which have singularities at the North and South Poles, the ORCA grid addresses this issue by repositioning the poles over land. The South Pole is located on the Antarctic continent, so no modification to the standard grid is necessary. However, the North Pole, located in the Arctic Ocean, is replaced by two points—one over North America and the other over Siberia. The ORCA grid is available in various horizontal resolutions, ranging from 2 degrees to 1/36 of a degree.

Figure 1. Tripolar grid used in the global ORCA configuration

The NEMO package also provides additional features, such as the ability to create and utilize nested regional grids with higher resolution through the bi-directional nesting package AGRIF. It supports generating parallel and/or asynchronous output with the efficient XIOS software, offers a coupling interface for integrating other climate system components using OASIS, enables the integration of external biogeochemical models, and includes utility tools for pre- and post-processing data.

The NEMO source code is written in Fortran 2008 and utilizes the MPI library for parallelization, employing a domain decomposition approach. Since 2022, the NEMO system has been distributed via the NEMO GitLab Repository. The most recent stable version of the model is 4.2.2, which was released in December 2023, while a new beta-5 version is currently being tested by the NEMO community.

4.1.2 IFS-FVM

The Finite-Volume Module (FVM, Smolarkiewicz et al. 2016; Kühnlein et al. 2019) represents a non-hydrostatic finite-volume dynamical core developed for the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) at ECMWF. The main goals of the numerical design are the suitability for cloud- and turbulence-scale resolutions and the adaptation to increasing multi-level parallelism, which pose problems to the operational spectral-transform IFS model.

Even if actively extended with new schemes, the baseline FVM numerical model solves the fully compressible equation considering comprehensive moist processes using efficient 3D semi-implicit finite-volume integration with conservative non-oscillatory advective transport for all prognostic variables and tracers. The 3D implicit schemes with variable coefficients provide robustness with respect to steep topography and the inherently conserving properties of the finite-volume advection schemes represent an important advantage compared to the non-conservative semi-Lagrangian advection in the spectral-transform IFS. Figure 2 illustrates the octahedral grid employed in the operational IFS at ECMWF, which can also be employed in FVM. Figure 3 highlights a snapshot from an early real weather re-forecast case study of tropical cyclone Irma with FVM coupled to the full IFS physical parametrizations.

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Figure 2: The locations of the IFS octahedral grid nodes are shown in (a), using for illustration the very coarse O24 grid example with 24 latitudes between the pole and equator. Panel (b) depicts the associated edges of the primary mesh connecting the nodes as applied in the context of FVM. Panel (c) provides the local spacing of the FV dual mesh for the O1280 grid corresponding to the highest-resolution deterministic forecast model currently at ECMWF (from Kühnlein et al. 2019).

Figure 3: Track of tropical cyclone Irma crossing the Caribbean simulated with FVM (left) and the spectral-transform IFS (right). The 5-day forecasts were initialized at 00 UTC on 4 September 2017. For this comparison, both models were configured with the same full IFS 43r3 subgrid-scale parametrization package and were uncoupled (i.e., no ocean component); also, both were using the identical O1280 octahedral grid of the IFS (about 9 km horizontal grid spacing) with 62 vertical levels. Colors of filled circles (every 6 h) indicate that FVM forecasts a deeper central pressure (in hPa) than the spectral-transform IFS for this case and the FVM forecast corresponds better with observed best track values (see hourglass symbols).

The original FVM was implemented in Fortran and optimized for CPU-based supercomputers. Results in Kühnlein et al. (2019) showed that FVM can provide competitive time-to-solution when compared with the spectral-transform IFS dynamical core, which ranks among the most efficient operational numerical weather prediction models. Nevertheless, the Fortran FVM only supports execution on CPUs and cannot take advantage of GPUs, and an extension with OpenACC directives to enable GPU execution was not considered. Instead, it has been decided to pursue a more sustainable and future-proof approach for its programming implementation. Building on the support by partners at CSCS and ETH Zurich in ESiWACE2, ECMWF rewrites and further develops FVM entirely in Python with the GT4Py domain-specific framework, in order to achieve broad hardware portability, high-performance execution on various GPU-accelerated supercomputers, an amenable model environment for hybrid modelling with machine learning, and improved user experience compared to current operational models. The label PMAP (Portable Model for Multi-Scale Atmospheric Prediction) is used to distinguish the new Python code and methods from the original FVM in Fortran.

4.2. DSL description

This section gives a more detailed overview of the DSL technologies used to optimize the climate models. A Domain Specific Language (DSL) is a programming language designed with a higher level of abstraction, tailored to address a particular set of problems. DSLs reduce complexity, increase productivity, and make code more readable and maintainable. Using concepts and rules specific to the domain or field it serves, DSLs are designed for use by domain experts rather than software developers. The main goal is the automatic creation of code optimized for a target machine. In the following, the PSyclone and GT4Py DSLs, used respectively in NEMO and IFS-FVM models, are better described.

4.2.1 PSyclone

PSyclone is a domain-specific language (DSL), and a code generation tool used in finite element, finite volume, and finite difference codes. It is designed to automate the process of optimizing, parallelizing and instrumenting High-Performance Computing (HPC) applications, with a particular focus on Fortran code. It is mainly used in scientific applications such as weather and climate models, where performance and efficiency are critical.

PSyclone automates the process of code generation. It takes a high-level description of a numerical weather or climate model and generates highly efficient, low-level code optimized for execution on high-performance computing systems. The tool supports multiple parallel programming models including shared-memory parallelism (via OpenMP), distributed-memory parallelism (via MPI), and accelerator-based parallelism (via OpenACC). This multi-platform support ensures that applications can run efficiently across a wide range of hardware configurations.

As a source-to-source compiler, PSyclone takes Fortran source code as input, applies various transformations to improve performance, and generates optimized Fortran code as output. The transformations are provided as user-defined scripts that enable optimizations and parallelization strategies to be applied to the code. These scripts allow users to choose between different parallel execution methods, such as OpenMP or OpenACC, ensuring that the code runs efficiently on various hardware architectures. By separating the scientific implementation of an application from the decisions related to optimization and parallelization, PSyclone allows developers to focus on the core scientific aspects of their work, while performance experts can independently focus on enhancing the efficiency of the code.

The core of PSyclone functionality lies in the Parallelisation System (PSy) layer, which is designed to provide parallel performance at the node level, tailored to the target architecture. This layer applies the transformations to enhance parallel execution to the PSyIR (PSyclone Internal Representation) tree. This tree, central for this process, is a high-level abstraction of the code; it can either be generated directly in Python or produced by parsing existing source code through a frontend.

In the case of NEMO, the PSyclone frontend parses the existing Fortran and creates the PSyIR, that is where the transformations are applied. The NEMO API is structured to treat the NEMO source code as if it were a PSy layer manually written, with all kernels in-lined. This method aligns with the NEMO Coding Conventions, ensuring consistency with the framework's established practices.

The PSy layer can be optimized for specific hardware architectures, including multi-core, many-core, GPGPUs, or hybrid configurations, without requiring any modifications to the scientific code. The final code produced by PSyclone is generated by passing the PSyIR tree to the NEMO Fortran "backends" (Figure 4). This approach enables the potential for performance portability across different hardware platforms.

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Figure 4. PSyclone as source-to-source compiler in NEMO environment

PSyclone latest stable release 2.5.0 is available through a GitHub¹ repository. It can be installed with the `'$pip install .'` command, as it is available as the Python Package Index (PyPI).

Many aspects of PSyclone can be set through a configuration file, `psyclone.cfg`. At execution-time, the user can define a custom configuration file to be used by specifying the path via the `PSYCLONE_CONFIG` environment variable. The configuration file is read by the Python `ConfigParser` class² and must be formatted accordingly. Currently, it is composed of a `DEFAULT` section (Figure 5), applicable to all APIs supported by PSyclone, and an optional API specific section. The specific API for NEMO code includes a `mapping-TYPE` entry, declaring a mapping for a certain loop level, specified as `TYPE`. An `index-order` entry is also present to specify the order in which loops are created when converting an implicit loop to an explicit loop.

```
[DEFAULT]
DEFAULTAPI = dynamo0.3
DEFAULTSTUBAPI = dynamo0.3
DISTRIBUTED_MEMORY = true
REPRODUCIBLE_REDUCTIONS = false
REPROD_PAD_SIZE = 8
PSYIR_ROOT_NAME = psyir_tmp
VALID_PSY_DATA_PREFIXES = profile, extract
```

Figure 5. Default section of the PSyclone configuration file

Figure 6 shows the NEMO specific section of a PSyclone configuration file. In the `mapping-TYPE` entry each value contains three `key:value` pairs. A value can be left empty if it is necessary or not available, but the key must always be provided. The essential keys are `var`, the variable name that represents the loop level, `start`, the first iteration of the loop, and `stop`, the last loop iteration. The mapping entries, such as `mapping-lon`, `mapping-lat`, and so on, correspond to the values in index order, etc.

```
mapping-lon = var: ji, start: 1, stop: jpi
mapping-lat = var: jj, start: 1, stop: jpj
mapping-levels = var: jk, start: 1, stop: jpk
mapping-tracers = var: jt, start: 1, stop:
mapping-unknown = var: , start: 1, stop:

index-order = lon, lat, levels, tracers
```

Figure 6. Specific section of the PSyclone configuration file for NEMO.

¹ <https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone> - PSyclone GitHub repository

² <https://docs.python.org/3/library/configparser.html>

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As an example, according to this convention, a NEMO loop that specifies `DO JJ=...` will be assigned the type `'lon'` by PSyclone, as the loop uses the variable name defined in the configuration file for the `'lon'` loop type.

The `mapping-unknown` entry has an empty value for the `'var'` key, which means the `'unknown'` type will be applied to any loop that doesn't match any of the variable names in the configuration file.

PSyclone's ability to transform source code from the NEMO ocean model can be easily tested using the examples available in the GitHub repository. These examples demonstrate how the `psyclone` command, the simplest way to run PSyclone, can be used to parallelize all loops over levels in tracer advection and tracer diffusion NEMO routines, using OpenMP and OpenACC transformations targeting both CPUs and GPUs.

Additional scripts are also provided to facilitate the use of PSyclone with the full NEMO model. These include a wrapper script, `process_nemo.py`, which enables users to control which source files are transformed, which have profiling instrumentation added, and which are ignored. There are also transformation scripts such as `acc_kernels_trans.py`, `omp_gpu_trans.py` and `acc_loops_trans.py`, which allow the generation of code targeting GPUs through the addition of OpenACC `kernel`, OpenMP and OpenACC `loops` directives, respectively. Moreover, the `omp_cpu_trans.py` transformation file, adding OpenMP directives for CPU threading parallelism, is available.

These scripts provided the starting point for the integration of PSyclone in the NEMO framework. Starting with the 5.0-beta release, the PSyclone processing step has been incorporated into the NEMO build system, which is based on the build sub-system of the Flexible Configuration Management system. The integration has been provided as an additional complete build process that includes regular source-code pre-processing followed by a modified Fortran compilation stage that performs PSyclone processing, resulting in "object" files that are PSyclone-processed source code files rather than traditional object files.

The integration of PSyclone into the NEMO build system aims to manage transformations across the whole set of source code files, usually the entire NEMO source code, with few exceptions. This integration includes dependency analysis to streamline recompilation during development and after applying source-code patches and ensures seamless integration into multi-stage build processes that already involve source-to-source transformations of the NEMO source code (e.g., AGRIF). Anyway, at this time, with 5.0-beta NEMO release, only the passthrough testing (where code is processed by PSyclone but not transformed) of all SETTE reference configurations with the latest release version of PSyclone is successful without changes to the code/scripts. Ultimately, this source-code transformation facility can be used to identify computational kernels and insert compiler directives in order to exploit parallelism. Achieving optimal performance by this method is not yet fully automatic but the transformations will be capable of generating code which will compile and run using GPU resources. At this stage, support for NVIDIA compilers and hardware is more mature but progress is underway to generalize the approach towards a wider range of platforms.

To enable the PSyclone integration, the `makenemo` script has been modified and extended with the introduction of a new option `'-p'` followed by the name of the PSyclone transformation to be applied.

In the example below, the PSyclone transformation `acc_kernel_trans` for the addition of OpenACC `kernels` directives across a large portion of the NEMO source code has been enabled. The transformation script has been taken from the PSyclone repository and added to the directory `sct/` of the NEMO framework, in order to provide a transformation option selectable via option `'-p'` of `makenemo`.

```
./makenemo -m auto-psyclone -n GYRE_tr_PSyclone -r GYRE_PISCES -p  
acc_kernels_trans del_key "key_top key_xios"
```

Figure 7. NEMO compilation with PSyclone support

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The new option triggers the call to `mk/sct_pyclone.sh` script, applying PSyclone to the NEMO source code. It is a wrapper script allowing to control the PSyclone processing steps and, eventually, can be modified by adding the files that fail to compile to the list of files to exclude from PSyclone compilation.

Definitely, with PSyclone processing, the build system processes the NEMO source code in three stages (or with AGRIF in four stages): CPP preprocessing, PSyclone processing, and the actual compilation. In the section 4.3.4 the setup of the environment and the tricks needed to successfully compile and execute the experimental configurations on the GPUs of the CMCC supercomputer are reported.

4.2.2 GT4Py

GridTools for Python (GT4Py) is a Python library to generate targeted high-performance implementations of stencil kernels as they are typical in weather and climate models. The library is developed and maintained by the Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS), ETH Zurich, and the Swiss Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology (MeteoSwiss), with contributions from international partners such as the Paul Allen Institute for Artificial Intelligence (AI2) and ECMWF. GT4Py has been released under the BSD-3-Clause license and is publicly available from the GitHub repository <https://github.com/GridTools/gt4py>.

The systematic separation of the code for domain science and performance engineering with the GT4Py approach offers significant advantages given the future requirement to continuously adapt the model to new hardware technology and to perform targeted hardware-specific optimization. The Python front-end and the abstraction of the grid connectivity, data layout, parallelization, optimization, and the hardware backends with the GT4Py approach provides a scientifically productive environment. GT4Py integrates with additional high-performance libraries such as DaCe (Data-Centric Parallel Programming; <https://github.com/spcl/dace>) for optimizing data flows and GHEX (Generic exascale-ready library for halo-exchange operations; <https://github.com/ghex-org/GHEX>) for distributed-memory functionalities.

The first public release of GT4Py (referred to as *gt4py.cartesian*; <https://pypi.org/project/gt4py/1.0.0/>) supports 3D structured grids employed in some regional atmospheric models and uses Python syntax but no valid Python semantics. The latest version of GT4Py (referred to as *gt4py.next*) supports general unstructured meshes and is fully embedded in Python with consistent semantics. Figure 8 provides a schematic depiction of the *gt4py.next* framework. Even though *gt4py.next* is at a fairly advanced stage, its development is ongoing, also partly as work within ESiWACE Task 2.2, with significant extension and optimization of the Intermediate Representation (IR), as well as toolchain optimizations and refinement of the front-end syntax. ICON (ICON4Py) at MeteoSwiss and FVM (PMAP) at ECMWF are two atmospheric models that are actively developed in Python with *gt4py.next*.

Figure 8: Schematic illustrating the *gt4py.next* framework.

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Two different PMAP configurations at differing development stages exist at the time of writing this report, but both are based on the same principles for the underlying fully compressible semi-implicit finite-volume schemes, and both will eventually be managed from the same software repository. These two configurations are (i) PMAP-LES: A regional model version on a 3D structured grid with large-eddy simulation (LES) capability implemented in Python with *gt4py.cartesian* and the GHEX library for the high-performance distributed functionalities; (ii) PMAP-GO: The global dynamical core with a horizontally-unstructured vertically-structured finite-volume discretisation and the octahedral grid of the operational IFS at ECMWF, implemented and developed in Python with *gt4py.next*. As in the Fortran FVM, PMAP-GO in Python employs ECMWF's Atlas framework for mesh generation and connectivities – for this Python bindings for the required Atlas functionalities were developed and the provided indirect addressing is incorporated in the stencil/field operators of *gt4py.next*.

4.3. Experimental configurations

This section provides a more detailed description of the selected experimental climate models configurations for NEMO and IFS-FVM. Moreover, the full porting activity is featured with details about the routines that have been ported, the changes and adaptation made to the code in order to be suitable for DSLs, and more in general, the development activities concerning the porting on GPU.

4.3.1 Med24

The Mediterranean Sea configuration is based on the operational Copernicus Marine Service Mediterranean analysis and forecasting system (MedFS).

In this configuration, the oceanic equations of motion are solved by NEMO using a horizontal resolution of $1/24^\circ \times 1/24^\circ$ (approximately 3.5 km) with 141 unevenly spaced vertical levels (Clementi et al., 2017b) and a time step of 120 seconds. The model covers the entire Mediterranean Sea, extending into the Atlantic to improve the exchanges with the Atlantic Ocean at the Strait of Gibraltar (Figure 9). The topography is derived from the GEBCO 30 arc-second grid³, filtered using a Shapiro filter, and manually adjusted in critical regions, such as the islands along the Eastern Adriatic coasts, the Gibraltar and Messina Straits, and the Atlantic border.

The NEMO model solves the primitive equations using a time-splitting method, explicitly resolving external gravity waves with a non-linear free surface formulation and time-varying vertical z-star coordinates. As advection scheme for active tracers (temperature and salinity) the mixed up-stream/MUSCL (Monotonic Upwind Scheme for Conservation Laws) is used. The vertical diffusion and viscosity terms are parameterized on the basis of the Richardson number (Pacanowsky and Philander, 1981). The vertical background viscosity is set to $1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ while the diffusivity value is set to $1.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. The horizontal eddy diffusivity and viscosity are set to $-1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$ and $-2.0 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$, respectively. A quadratic bottom drag coefficient, using a logarithmic formulation, is applied according to Maraldi et al. (2013), and the model employs vertical partial cells to fit the bottom depth shape.

The model is forced by momentum, heat, and water fluxes, computed interactively using the MFS-bulk formulae (Pettenuzzo et al., 2010), with 6-hour temporal resolution and $1/10^\circ$ horizontal-resolution analysis fields from ECMWF. Model-predicted surface temperatures are also considered (details on air-sea physics are provided in Tonani et al., 2008). The water balance is computed as the difference between evaporation and precipitation/runoff. Evaporation is derived from latent heat flux, precipitation is provided as daily averages by ECMWF, and runoff is based on climatological monthly data from 39 rivers. The Dardanelles Strait is treated as

³ http://www.gebco.net/data_and_products/gridded_bathymetry_data_gebco_30_second_grid/

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a lateral open boundary condition, using the GLO-MFC daily Analysis and Forecast product along with daily climatology from a Marmara Sea box model (Maderich et al., 2015). Tidal potential is computed across the domain for the 8 major constituents in the Mediterranean (M2, S2, N2, K2, K1, O1, P1, Q1), and tidal forcing is applied along the Atlantic lateral boundaries using tidal elevation data from the FES2014 tidal model (Carrere et al., 2016) and tidal currents from the TUGO model (Lynch and Gray, 1979).

The model is nested in the Atlantic within the Copernicus Marine Global analysis and forecasting system's daily dataset, with a horizontal resolution of $1/12^\circ$ and 50 vertical levels (Copernicus Marine product GLOBAL_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_001_024). A Flather boundary condition is applied for barotropic velocities in the Atlantic (South, West, East), while a flow relaxation scheme is used for baroclinic velocities and tracers.

In the preliminary step of the analysis, a simplified configuration was used, excluding tides and rivers. In this early setup, the model was not nested in the Atlantic, and no boundary conditions were applied.

Figure 9. Model domain and bathymetry [m] of the Med24 configuration.

4.3.2 GLOB16

GLOB16 is a global ocean and sea ice configuration based on the NEMO code version 4.2.2 (Madec et al., 2023). It builds on earlier versions described in Iovino et al. (2016, 2023), with significant updates reflecting ongoing code improvements. The model has been applied in various oceanographic studies (e.g., Treguier et al., 2023; Manral et al., 2023) and serves as the primary modelling framework for the global ocean forecasting system at the CMCC (<https://gofs.cmcc.it/>). GLOB16 employs a nonuniform tripolar grid with a horizontal resolution of $1/16^\circ$, corresponding to about 6.9 km at the equator, with finer grid spacing toward the poles. The grid spacing increases poleward following the cosine of latitude, reaching approximately 5.5 km at 40° latitude, 4 km at 60° , and a minimum of around 2 km near Victoria Island. The grid consists of 5762×3963 horizontal grid points. Zonal and meridional scaling factors are illustrated in Figures 10a and 10b.

The vertical coordinate system of the model is defined by fixed depth levels, comprising 98 vertical layers. The grid spacing ranges from roughly 1 meter near the surface to 160 meters in the deep ocean (see Figure 10c).

The ocean component of the model is a finite-difference, hydrostatic, primitive equation ocean general circulation model. It uses a linearized free surface, a free-slip lateral friction condition, and an Arakawa C grid. Horizontal momentum and tracer equations incorporate biharmonic viscosity and diffusivity schemes, respectively. For tracer advection, the model employs a Total Variance Dissipation (TVD) scheme (Zalesak, 1979). Vertical mixing is achieved using the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) closure scheme (Blanke and Delecluse, 1993). Background vertical diffusion and viscosity coefficients account for vertical mixing induced by the processes that are unresolved in the model. In case of static instability, vertical eddy mixing of both momentum and tracers is enhanced. The turbulent closure model does not apply specific modifications in ice-covered regions. Bottom friction is quadratic, and a diffusive bottom boundary layer scheme is included. All configurations use the EOS80 equation of state for seawater (Fofonoff and Millard, 1983), with potential temperature and practical salinity treated as prognostic state variables.

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The ocean component is coupled with the Sea Ice Modelling Integrated Initiative (SI3, Vanconpenolle et al., 2023), which is based on the LIM3 model (Rousset et al., 2015), with additional functionality incorporated from CICE (Hunke et al., 2015). Both the ocean and sea ice components use the same horizontal grid, ensuring consistency between these coupled systems. SI3 is fully integrated into the model's code and is activated through the Surface Boundary Code (SBC) module. The sea ice code is based on the Arctic Ice Dynamics Joint EXperiment (AIDJEX) framework, using a 2+1D continuum approach and an ice thickness distribution framework. It incorporates the conservation of horizontal momentum, elastic-viscous-plastic rheology (Hunke and Dukowicz, 1997), and energy-conserving halo-thermodynamics. In the horizontal direction, the model uses a curvilinear orthogonal grid, while in the vertical, it employs equally spaced layers. In thickness space, the model is divided into five categories with predefined boundaries.

Figure 10. Zonal (a) and meridional (b) scale factors (in km). Dashed contours start from 6 km in the equatorial region and decrease poleward with a 1 km interval. c) Vertical level thickness (lower) as function of cumulative depth (in m).

4.3.3 Baroclinic wave benchmark

The global baroclinic wave benchmark from the Dynamical Core Model Intercomparison Project (DCMIP) 2016 is used to validate the new PMAP implementations in Python with GT4Py. It has been used previously to compare the FVM with the spectral-transform IFS dynamical core in Kühnlein et al. 2019. Similar basic validation, performance and scalability studies based on the baroclinic wave benchmark have been performed with other models (e.g., Fuhrer et al. 2018). Details on the setup and the relevant flow dynamics aspects are discussed in Ullrich et al. 2014.

Figure 11 presents numerical simulations with the original Fortran FVM and the newly implemented PMAP-GO, both using the same numerical schemes, the same octahedral grid, and are set up with the identical initial conditions of the baroclinic wave benchmark. The results are shown on day 15, which is deep into the nonlinear stage of the global baroclinic wave evolution. Typically, this test case is analyzed earlier on day 10, but here we

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deliberately do the comparison at later stages to expose the smallest differences in the implementation of the underlying algorithms. In addition, the presented simulations have all used exclusively single-precision computations. The comparison reveals very close agreement on the late day 15, but nevertheless some small differences appear in the shown meridional wind field, which is expected because the details in the actual implementation and optimisation exist.

Figure 11: Global baroclinic wave benchmark simulation after 15 days with the newly developed PMAP-GO that is fully implemented in Python with GT4Py.next, alongside the reference result obtained with the original FVM in Fortran. Meridional velocity ($m s^{-1}$, shaded) is shown at an altitude of 2 km. Both PMAP-GO and FVM employed single-precision (32-bit) computations and the IFS octahedral grid O160 (Malardel et al. 2016), which was illustrated in Figure 2.

4.3.4 Porting activities on CMCC supercomputer

As documented in the Milestone M2.3, the first challenge during the porting activities was the setup of a working NVIDIA environment. Although on the CMCC machine the NVIDIA compilers and libraries suite are yet installed and can be easily loaded as module <NVIDIA HPC SDK Version 22.3>, many adjustments were needed to be able to have successful runs. First, a new installation of HDF5 and NetCDF libraries, needed to compile and run NEMO, has been done, since those provided on the system were built with the INTEL compiler and not suitable to work with the NVIDIA compiler. Nevertheless, since the job continued to fail during the execution phase due to an error of the PMIx library, causing an MPI_ABORT that killed all MPI processes in the communicator, a new installation of the OpenMPI compiler was necessary. In particular, OpenMPI configure was needed to use external hwloc, libevent and PMIx libraries to ensure proper operation.

Definitely, to solve the issue, hwloc and libevent libraries have been installed. Then the PMIx library has been built against these new packages. Finally, OpenMPI compiler has been configured and built, specifying the location of the PMIx, libevent, and hwloc packages and adding a directive to directly use PMIx installation of these libraries.

Moreover, a further upgrade to OpenMPI compiler has been done with respect to the Milestone M2.3, with the aim to enable the proper model execution on multiple GPU nodes. As documented in the previous experiments, to test the configurations using multiple GPUs nodes, it was needed to select the shared mode for the GPUs in the submission script, in order the jobs don't get stalled. As seen in the results of M2.3 report, if on the one

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hand this selection allows the use of a greater number of GPUs, on the other it significantly worsened the inter-nodes scalability. Using the command line utility `nvidia-smi`, intended to aid in the management and monitoring of NVIDIA GPU devices, it was seen that in the shared mode only a subset of the allocated resources was being used effectively.

For this reason, new investigations have been carried out to try solving this failure, leading to a new OpenMPI compiler installation, based on the 4.1.6 version, taking into account the LSF support (`--with-lsf` and `--with-lsf-libdir` options in the `configure` command) and other optimization features, such as the Mellanox Hierarchical Collectives support (`--with-hcoll` option in the `configure` command) and the Unified Communication X library support (`--with-ucx` option in the `configure` command). This last one, in particular, is an acceleration library designed to achieve the highest performance for HPC applications. It has a broad range of optimizations for achieving low-software overheads in communication path which allows near native-level performance. UCX supports side tag matching, one-sided communication semantics, efficient memory registration and a variety of enhancements which increase the scalability and performance of HPC applications significantly. UCX supports includes also the InfiniBand transports - such as Unreliable Datagram (UD), Reliable Connected (RC) and Dynamically Connected (DC) -, Shared Memory communication with support for KNEM, CMA and XPMEM, RoCE, TCP and CUDA. In Figure 12 the script with the new options used to properly build the new OpenMPI version is shown. Afterward, the HDF5 and NetCDF libraries have been rebuilt with the new compiler. Finally, Figure 13 shows the environment used for the experiments, where:

- `/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/shared/lib` directory contains `hwloc`, `libevent` and `PMIX` libraries
- `/work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-ompi-gpu/lib` directory includes `HDF5`, `NetCDF-C` and `NetCDF-F`
- `/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler_gpu/bin` directory includes the Open MPI compiler

```
module purge
module load gcc-12.2.0
module load nvhpc-22.3-nompi/22.3
module load nvsdk22/hpcx-2.10/hpcx-stack

EXT_LIB=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/shared
DST=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/
ncl=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/ompi_last
cuda=/juno/opt/nvidia/hpc-sdk-22.3/Linux_x86_64/22.3/cuda
lsf=/opt/ibm/lfsuite/lsf/10.1

./configure --prefix=${DST} CC=nvc CXX=nvc++ FC=nvfortran F90=nvfortran \
  CFLAGS="-fPIC" FCFLAGS="-Mstandard -fPIC" LDFLAGS="-fPIC" \
  --with-pmix=$EXT_LIB --with-libevent=$EXT_LIB --with-hwloc=$EXT_LIB \
  --with-xpmem --with-cma \
  --enable-shared --enable-static --without-tm --enable-mpi-cxx \
  --with-ucx=$ucx --enable-mca-no-build=btl-uct --disable-wrapper-runpath \
  --with-wrapper-ldflags=-Wl,-rpath --with-lsf=$lsf --with-lsf-libdir=$LSF_LIBDIR \
  --enable-mpirun-prefix-by-default --with-cuda=$cuda --with-hcoll=$hcoll \
  --enable-mpi1-compatibility --with-hcoll=$hcoll
make -j 72
make install
```

Figure 12. Script used to build the new OpenMPI version

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```
module purge
module load intel-2021.6.0/perl-xml-parser/2.44-27mmx
module load intel-2021.6.0/perl/5.36.0-jj4hw
module load gcc-12.2.0/12.2.0
module load nvhpc-22.3-nompi/22.3
module load nvsdk22/hpcx-2.10/hpcx-stack

nsl=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/mpi_last
openmpi=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler_gpu
export MPI_HOME=$openmpi
export PATH=$openmpi/bin:$PATH
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$nsl/lib:$openmpi/lib/openmpi:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
export LIBRARY_PATH=$nsl/lib:$LIBRARY_PATH
export OPAL_PREFIX=$openmpi
export CPATH=$openmpi/include:$CPATH
export OMPI_HOME=$openmpi
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$openmpi/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
export LD_RUN_PATH=$openmpi/lib/openmpi:$LD_RUN_PATH
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/shared/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH

export PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/shared/bin:$PATH
export CPATH=$openmpi/include:$CPATH
export CPATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/shared/include:$CPATH
export PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-gpu/bin:$PATH
export CPATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-gpu/include:$CPATH
export LIBRARY_PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-gpu/lib:$LIBRARY_PATH
export LD_RUN_PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-gpu/lib:$LD_RUN_PATH
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-gpu/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
```

Figure 13. NVIDIA environment built for the tests

As already done in M2.3, the new compiler and libraries have been used to build the architecture file to be specified in the `./makenemo` command (Figure 7). The `build_arch-auto.sh` script provided with NEMO package, has been used for this aim. Allowing to automatically determine some architecture-specific configuration settings, it facilitates the generation of the architecture configuration file. Also, in this case the use of PGI's 'managed memory' option to deal with data movement between CPU/GPU is needed. Figure 14 shows the newly generated arch-file for the CMCC JUNO supercomputer equipped with 20 GPU NVIDIA A100. In order to use PSyclone, the NEMO configuration file has to include the `"%PSYCLONE_HOME"` variable set to the PSyclone installation directory path.

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```
# Mon Nov 4 10:35:28 CET 2024
#
%NCDF_C_PREFIX      /work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-gpu
%NCDF_F_PREFIX      /work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-gpu
%HDF5_PREFIX        /work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-gpu

%PSyclone_HOME      /users_home/cmcc/fm27215/.local

%ATOMIC_PREFIX      /juno/opt/gcc/12.2.0
%NCDF_INC           -I%NCDF_F_PREFIX/include          -I%NCDF_C_PREFIX/include          -
I%ATOMIC_PREFIX/include
%NCDF_LIB           -L%NCDF_F_PREFIX/lib -lnetcdf      -L%NCDF_C_PREFIX/lib -lnetcdf      -
L%HDF5_PREFIX/lib -lhdf5_hl -lhdf5 -lhdf5_fortran -lz -lm -L%ATOMIC_PREFIX/lib64 -
latomic

%CPP                cpp -Dkey_nosignedzero
%FC                 mpifort
%FCFLAGS            -i4 -r8 -O3 -Minfo=accel -Mneginfo -acc=gpu -fpic -fortranlibs -
ta=tesla:managed
%FFLAGS             %FCFLAGS
%LD                 %FC
%LDFLAGS            -lstc++ -lz -lgpfs -acc=gpu -ta=tesla:managed
%FPPFLAGS           -P -traditional
%AR                 ar
%ARFLAGS            rs
%MK                 make
%USER_INC           %NCDF_INC
%USER_LIB           %NCDF_LIB
```

Figure 14. *arch-auto* file automatically generated

The execution environment settings made so far enable the NVIDIA compiler to successfully compile the GYRE, MED24, and GLOB16 setups using PSyclone v2.5.0 and the NEMO main branch after the v4.2.2 release on the JUNO CMCC supercomputer. Since the release of NEMO v4.2.2, significant improvements have been made in both PSyclone integration and NVIDIA compiler compatibility. As a result, modifications to the NEMO source code needed in the first tests and described in the M2.3 document are no longer required.

Anyway, to prevent additional errors, PSyclone processing has been explicitly disabled for certain files that fail to compile by adding their names to the exclusion list in `sct_psyclone.sh` (e.g., `[["${FILENAME}" == 'obs_types.f90']] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'`). Figure 15 shows the list of files that were excluded in order to compile the GYRE, MED24, and GLOB16 configurations using PSyclone v2.5.0.

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```
if [ ${PSYCLONE_VERSION} == "2.5.0" ]; then
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'timing.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'lbclnk.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'prtctl.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'stopar.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'stopts.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'fldread.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdyini.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'ldfslp.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'domtile.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'zdfgls.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icbdia.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcssr.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'datsd.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_grid.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_surf_def.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_profiles_def.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_aver_g_h2d.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_types.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_read_prof.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_read_surf.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_andreas.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_coare3p0.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_coare3p6.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_ncar.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_ice_an05.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_ice_lg15.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_ice_lu12.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_mfs.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn_rhg_ev_p.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn_adv_umx.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icbut1.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'diaar5.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'diadct.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdydyn2d.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'dynhpg.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'traadv_mus.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'traadv_qck.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'traadv_ubs.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'trabbl.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'zdfmfc.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'fldread_ECMWF.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdyice.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'lbcnfd.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icectl.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn_adv.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn_rhg_vp.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdydta.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'trdra.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdydyn2d.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdydyn3d.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdytra.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'iom.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'zdfdrg.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
```

Figure 15. List of files excluded from P_Syclone processing in sct_psyclone.sh script

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As already discussed in the M2.3 document, issues remain for a complete execution on GPUs of the MED24 configuration. A simplified version was in fact used for the tests, omitting tides and rivers. This decision was made due to challenges encountered when attempting to port the full configuration to the NEMO main branch or the 5.0-beta release. During execution, problems occurred after reading the boundary-related files, which seemed to have mismatched dimensions and incorrect data sizes, leading to a segmentation fault error. This issue, probably linked to the NVIDIA compiler or environment, has been temporarily circumvented by disabling the unstructured open boundaries through the namelist in this phase.

Similar issues have been encountered with the GLOB16 configuration during execution, specifically during the ice shelf initialization, where the job hangs without generating any errors. Previously, such issues were resolved by adding the relevant routine to the `ACC_IGNORE` list in the `psct-acc_kernels_trans.py` PSyclone transformation script, which prevents PSyclone from adding OpenACC directives to routines that cause problems with the NVIDIA compiler or are unnecessary. However, this approach does not resolve the issue in the ice shelf initialization case. For now, performance analysis has been focused on the GYRE configuration, which uses a resolution similar to that of GLOB16.

4.4. Tests and Performance Analysis

This section details the performance tests conducted on the target machine, the CMCC JUNO supercomputer. The JUNO machine is equipped with 160 Compute nodes type Lenovo SD630 v2 and 10 Hybrid nodes type (CPU+GPU) Lenovo SR670 v2. Each Compute node is equipped with 72 Intel Xeon P. 8360 processors and 512 GB of RAM. Each hybrid node is composed of 72 Intel Xeon P. 8360Y processors and 2 GPU NVIDIA A100 40GB. The main memory per node is 1024 GB. The machine uses the Spectrum LSF v. 10.2 as the batch queuing system.

The NVIDIA environment employed during the compilation stage, shown in Figure 13, was also used during the execution phase. Figure 16 provides an example of the submission script used for the test. The “g_devel” GPU queue is one of the available queues on the JUNO machine. The GPU requirements for the job can be set using the “-gpu” option in the LSF scheduler `#BSUB` directives. By default, the number is per host. During execution, the GPU mode can be either a shared or exclusive process. On the CMCC machine, the default mode is an exclusive process. So far, for multi-node jobs, shared mode was required to prevent the job from stalling. As indicated by the previous results reported in M2.3 report, choosing shared mode notably reduced the performance, increasing the execution time. With the new environment described in the previous section, this constraint is no longer needed, allowing the use of exclusive process mode and a correct resource exploitation.

In some cases, as in the GYRE50 configuration tests for example, the multi-nodes jobs stopped due to instabilities issues after a few time-steps. This required setting some parameters at run time. In fact, OpenMPI is a highly customizable system; it can be configured via configuration files, command line parameters, and environment variables. The main functionality of OpenMPI configuration system is through the Modular Component Architecture (MCA) that is used to customize OpenMPI behaviour at run-time. To solve this issue some MCA command line parameters and some environment variables have been set. Specifically, as reported in Figure 16, the `OMPI_MCA_ompi_fabric_type` global param has been set to `ucx` to indicate that this component should be used. Moreover, since by default, Open MPI doesn't use UCX for TCP-only and/or Shared Memory-only communication, the workaround was to set the following MCA options via `mpirun`, by adding the two CLI options “-mca opal_common_ucx_tls all -mca opal_common_ucx_devices all”. Finally, setting the variable `OMPI_MCA_btl_openib_allow_ib` to 1 is required in order to get the correct connectivity.

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```
#!/bin/bash

#BSUB -q g_devel
#BSUB -J GYRE_GPU
#BSUB -n 4
#BSUB -P 0603
#BSUB -o job_1c.out
#BSUB -e job_1c.err
#BSUB -gpu "num=2"
#BSUB -R "span[ptile=2]"
#BSUB -x

source /work/cmcc/fm27215/ESiWACE3/nemo_5.0-beta/load_Pyclone_env_gpu

echo "Debugging session started on nodes: $LSB_MCPU_HOSTS"
export CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES=0,1
export OMPI_MCA_ompi_fabric_type=ucx
export OMPI_MCA_btl_openib_allow_ib=1

mpirun --mca opal_common_ucx_tls all --mca opal_common_ucx_devices all ./nemo
```

Figure 16- Submission script used for the tests on GPUs

4.4.1 Med24

The MED24 configuration tests were conducted over a 6-hour simulation period, corresponding to 180 time steps, with each step lasting 120 seconds. To obtain more detailed statistics, the full *timing.output* file was generated by activating the related option in the namelist file.

The experiments were performed using an increasing number of resources, either CPUs or GPUs. The following table shows the elapsed time (in seconds) extracted from the *timing.output* file for the MED24 configuration run on CPU and GPU nodes. The tests were compared by running the same simulation on 1 GPU versus 1 CPU (equivalent to 36 cores). Similarly, the elapsed time for running the simulation on 72 Intel Xeon P. cores was compared to the time taken by 2 NVIDIA A100 GPUs, and so on. In addition to what is documented in the M2.3 report, the tests on GPUs have been performed with the new environment, too, where the GPUs exclusive process mode can be properly activated.

MED24	Intel Xeon P. 8360	NVIDIA A100	NVIDIA A100 new_env
1 core	43.806		
2 cores	21.717		
4 cores	13.568		
8 cores	5.494		
36 cores (1 CPU) / 1 GPU	1.157	3.875	3751
72 cores (2 CPUs) / 2 GPUs	614	2.163	2184

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MED24	Intel Xeon P. 8360	NVIDIA A100	NVIDIA A100 new_env
144 cores (4 CPUs) / 4 GPUs	296	3.853	1610
288 cores (8 CPUs) / 8 GPUs	153	4.113	1108

Table 1. Elapsed times (s) of the MED24 configuration running on CPUs and GPUs with the previous (central column) and the new (right column) environment

The execution times are also depicted graphically in Figure 17, which illustrates the scalability of the MED24 configuration on both CPUs and GPUs. As expected, the main difference from the analysis reported in the M2.3 report regards the multi-nodes GPUs runs. Since using the new environment the GPUs exclusive process mode is properly used, the execution times decrease when multiple nodes of the CMCC cluster are used. Anyway using CPUs the elapsed time continues to remain always faster than the time on GPUs (~70%).

Figure 17. Scalability of the MED24 configuration on CPUs and GPUs

For NVIDIA GPUs, the Nsight Systems tool is available for profiling different aspects of computation in order to better understand the cause of lack of performance on GPUs. The Nsight Systems CLI is already present in nvhpc-sdk22 modules on CMCC Juno machine and it can be used to profile the code in the system. To run the program through the Nsight command line profiler 'nsys', the submission line must be modified as shown in Figure 18. The '-t' flag tells the profiler what aspects it should profile, e.g. CUDA and OpenACC code, the '-f' flag tells the profiler that it can override existing output file, The '-o' flag tells the profiler the name we would like for the output file.

```
mpirun nsys profile -t cuda,openacc -f true -o kernels ./nemo
```

Figure 18. Command used to profile nemo with Nsight tool

As a test, only 10 time steps of the MED24 configuration have been simulated using 1 GPU with Nsight profiler.

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Figure 19 shows the user interface of Nsight. It has three main areas and two drop down menus that control what is shown in the different areas. 'Timeline view' and 'Event view' are the default views that can be seen when Nsight is opened.

Figure 19. User interface of NVIDIA Nsight System

By choosing one of the various 'Event View' options, the profiler displays how much runtime each function used, presented in different ways. In the image below, the Bottom-Up View is selected, which sorts functions by placing the most time-consuming ones at the top. In this case, the NEMO 'traadv_mus' routine is identified as the most resource intensive.

Figure 20. Bottom-Up Event View of NVIDIA Nsight System

Selecting and filtering a single time step of the timeline view the previous metric is recomputed and the percentage of the NEMO 'traadv_mus' routine results higher. Moreover, in the main timeline view, the usage of different APIs and the amount of CPU and GPU usage can be examined by clicking the arrow next to our GPU name. This reveals the percentages of Kernel usage and Memory usage. In the current profile, approximately

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61,8% of the Kernel resources are being utilized, indicating that the GPU is dedicating only 61,8% of its time to performing meaningful computations (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Percentage of GPU usage (Kernel and Memory usage) for one NEMO time step

The timeline related to the 'traadv_mus' NEMO routine has been captured and filtered (Figure 22). These actions trigger the re-computation of the statistics which reveal that it does not use the GPU at all, the GPU results completely idle. In fact, it is among the routines excluded from PScylone processing (Figure 11). Consequently, as next steps, it is necessary to proceed to make the 'tra_adv_mus' routine compliant with PScylone transformations.

Figure 22. Percentage of GPU usage for the 'traadv_mus' NEMO routine

Moreover, the CUDA GPU Summary (Kernels/MemOps) table related to the single time-step has been extracted from the available Nsight Stats System Views (Figure 23). The statistics highlight that most of the time is spent in copying data to and from the GPU while the kernel that primarily uses the GPU is 'dynspg_ts'.

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Figure 23. CUDA GPU Summary (Kernels/MemOps) view related to one NEMO time step

By selecting the routine 'dynspg_ts' in the Timeline View the statistics are recomputed (Figure 24). It can be noted that, in this case, the GPU is spending 69,7% of its time actually doing useful computation, while the remaining time it is dealt with memory transfer from host to device (20,4%) and from device to host (9,9%). Analysing the PScyclone processed code structure of the kernel can be seen that there are many '\$acc kernels', '\$acc end kernels' directives alternating between calls to other routines and/or conditional statements. This causes the breaks of GPU computation and many transfers to/from memory. An improvement of the GPU exploitation could consider restructuring code, where possible, to allow openacc directives to be applied to larger portions of code without discontinuity.

Figure 24. Percentage of GPU usage and CUDA GPU Summary (Kernels/MemOps) view related to dynspg_ts NEMO routine

4.4.2 GLOB16

The same tests of MED24 were conducted for the GYRE 50 configuration. As mentioned earlier, due to some unresolved issues that arose during the ice shelf initialization phase of GLOB16 execution, the performance analysis has been performed on a high-resolution GYRE configuration. For this test, a global domain of 1502 x 1002 x 31 grid points was used, with a simulation length of 6 hours, corresponding to 108 time steps. The duration of each time step was set to 200 seconds in order to closely replicate the GLOB16 configuration.

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Higher-resolution configurations led to additional issues during the execution phase on GPUs, which will require further investigation.

The following table reports the elapsed time of the GYRE configuration on both CPU and GPU nodes. In this case the time obtained using the previous environment (using share mode in GPUs setting) and the new environment on GPUs is also compared. The testing approach, consisting in using an increasing number of resources - CPUs or GPUs - was the same as described earlier for the other configuration. As resulted from the MED24 tests, here the main differences from the analysis reported in M2.3 regard the multi-nodes GPUs runs, too. Also in this case the execution times decrease when multiple GPU nodes of the CMCC cluster are used and the GPUs exclusive mode process is properly set. Anyway, using CPUs once again gives better results.

GYRE 50	Intel Xeon P. 8360	NVIDIA A100	NVIDIA A100 new_env
1 core	2.111		
2 cores	928		
4 cores	579		
8 cores	294		
36 cores (1 CPU) / 1 GPU	101	1.306	1295
72 cores (2 CPUs) / 2 GPUs	88	724	722
144 cores (4 CPUs) / 4 GPUs	47	1.174	623
288 cores (8 CPUs) / 8 GPUs	24	1.742	386

Table 2. Elapsed times (s) of the GYRE50 configuration running on CPUs and GPUs with the previous (central column) and the new (right column) environment

The times from the previous table were used to create the graph in Figure 25, which illustrates the scalability of the GYRE 50 configuration on both CPUs and GPUs. As can be easily noted, the execution time is always better using CPUs. Anyway during these tests the execution times reduce when multiple nodes of the CMCC cluster are utilized.

Figure 25. Scalability of the GYRE50 configuration on CPUs and GPUs

4.4.3 Baroclinic wave benchmark

We highlight selected results from our portability and scalability testing on different HPC systems and hardware architectures. Figure 26 shows measured runtimes of the PMAP-GO dynamical core on the new NVIDIA Grace Hopper system at CSCS. So far, we have considered either the four Grace CPUs (of one node) or one GH200 GPU (out of the four on one node) – note that the multi-GPU version of PMAP-GO could not yet be tested on this system but these tests will become possible in Q1 2025 and then reported at the next future occasion. The single-node PMAP-GO simulations in Figure 26 executed well on the Grace CPUs and the GH200 GPU, see the figure caption for more details. We found that the new GH200 provided significant performance gains compared to the previous hardware at CSCS (not shown), consistent with increased memory bandwidth. Overall, the results demonstrate the ability of PMAP-GO to benefit from these computing advances, but still significant further refinement and optimization of PMAP-GO and *gt4py.next* is upcoming, before a systematic 1-1 comparison study with the spectral-transform IFS will be performed.

The high-performance distributed multi-node model could already be tested with the PMAP-LES regional configuration. Figure 27 shows weak scaling of the model across a large number of CPUs and GPUs, with highest resolutions at O(1km) in this near-global latitude-longitude grid setup as in Fuhrer et al. 2018. Here, both the previous Piz Daint system at CSCS and the LUMI system at CSC were tested; please refer to the caption of Figure 27 for further details. Weak scaling appears very good in all tested configurations (apart from one outlier for the CPU/FP64 results at 2048 MPI ranks on LUMI, but this was likely caused by machine traffic rather than a model-specific problem), using either exclusively single or double precision computations.

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Figure 26: PMAP-GO dynamical core runtimes for the global baroclinic wave benchmark obtained with the NVIDIA Grace Hopper GH200 architecture of the new Alps supercomputer at CSCS. Shown are runtimes for PMAP-GO using either four Grace CPUs with 288 cores in total (blue bars) or one GH200 GPU (orange bars); note we employed all available CPUs but only one out of four GPUs of one Alps compute node. Two different octahedral grids O160 and O400 with 101 vertical levels were tested here.

Figure 27: Portability and scalability studies on the Piz Daint (top panel) and LUMI (bottom panel) supercomputers. The values shown are from 100 timestep simulations of the moist baroclinic wave benchmark using the structured-grid PMAP in near-global configuration (as in Fuhrer et al. 2018). The plot shows good weak scaling of the model from 32 to 2048 ranks while keeping the same workload per rank, i.e., the goal is to achieve constant execution time. The (equatorial) physical grid spacings are indicated in light gray color in the upper part of the plots. The task distribution layout and the CPU and GPU resources assigned to each task are specified at the horizontal axis. Two GridTools (GT) powered backends for CPU and GPU were studied along with one GPU backend leveraging the DaCe framework. We show the results for PMAP using either entirely double (FP64, filled) or single (FP32, hatched) precision computations.

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6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

Regarding the FVM/PMAP/GT4Py contribution no significant changes to the plans have occurred and no significant difficulty was encountered.

Regarding PSyclone + NEMO several difficulties have been encountered during the deployment of the system software. First of all, many problems related to the MPI library and CUDA environment have been addressed, starting from the error during the model execution phase deriving from the OpenMPI installation in NVIDIA SDK package on the CMCC target machine, that was solved re-installing in the proper way the hwloc, libevent and PMIx libraries, and re-building OpenMPI compiler against of them, to the scalability problems arising during multiple nodes executions. These last ones were solved taking into account the LSF support, and other optimisation features (such as the Mellanox Hierarchical Collectives and the UCX library support) in the OpenMPI installation.

Moreover several modules of NEMO were still not supported by PSyclone `acc_kernel` transformation, used for the targeting on GPUS, resulting in error during the compilation phase. Therefore, the PSyclone processing step has been disabled for the files that fail to compile by adding their name to the list of `sct_psyclone.sh`.

Finally, some difficulties have also been encountered in porting the full configurations to the nemo main or 5.0-beta release. During execution, issues arose after reading the boundary-related files of the MED24, which appeared to have incorrect dimensions and data sizes, resulting in a segmentation fault error. The error, probably related to the NVIDIA compiler, has been temporarily bypassed, disabling the unstructured open boundaries by `namelist` in this phase and using a simplified version of the configuration, excluding tides and rivers. Issues are arising during the execution phase of the GLOB16 configuration, too. In particular, during the

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ice shelf initialisation, the job remains hanging without errors and no solution has been found. So the performance analysis has been carried out on the GYRE configuration using a resolution similar to the GLOB16 case.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

The use of domain specific languages allows for performance portability in the use of heterogeneous computing hardware, particularly with modern accelerators such as GPUs. As a result, the models can be easily adapted to new hardware technology, including performing targeted hardware-specific optimization. This eventually allows them to perform larger simulations and to address more significant problems with Europe's HPC resources. With the integration of domain specific libraries in leading European software (such as NEMO, PMAP), this work is fostering the development of world-leading software for high performance in Europe.

8. Sustainability

The deliverable documents the work that has been conducted in PSyclone and GT4Py, which are open-source libraries, therefore allowing for sustainable development of the software beyond the lifetime of this project. The developments for NEMO are partly open-source and PMAP is also planned to become open-source. As the tools are linked and implemented to larger modelling efforts – in particular, NEMO, PMAP-GO, PSyclone and GT4Py – they will be of interest and continued by the model and DSL consortia. This is in particular true for the developments in GT4Py as the backend of the DSL can be used in several weather and climate models, also including ICON and FV3.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The tools are targeting weather and climate modellers in general but in particular the modelling consortia around NEMO and PMAP. The results will be shared with other scientists within the consortia and developments will feed into future model versions for NEMO and PMAP and new versions of PSyclone and GT4Py.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <u>open access</u> be provided to this publication?

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

The DSLs are developed as open-source software.